

**Complexes of Sb(III) and Sb(V) Halides
with Ketonic Schiff Bases Derived from
S-Methyldithiocarbazate**

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THE Schiff bases obtained by the condensation of methyl or benzyl esters of dithiocarbazic acid with aliphatic and aromatic aldehydes or ketones have provided an array of N-S donor multidentate ligands and their transition metal chelates have received considerable attention due to their remarkable carcinostatic properties¹⁻³. Organotin(IV) chlorides yield five and six coordinate organotin(IV) chelates⁴ when they interact with the sodium salt of such Schiff bases.

The bases are reported to exist in the NH tautomeric form (Ia) in the solid state, while the SH form (Ib) is predominant² in solution. In this communication we report the syntheses of SbX₃.L and SbCl₄.L by the direct interaction of antimony halides with the Schiff bases in dichloromethane and their characterization.

R=Me; R'=Me(HL-1), Et(HL-2),
Ph(HL-3) and R=R'=Ph(HL-4).

Experimental

SbCl₃ (Albright and Wilson, U.K.), SbCl₅ (Allied Chemicals, U.S.A.) were used after distillation under reduced pressure. SbBr₃ (Reidel) was used as such and ketones (all B.D.H.) were used after purification by conventional methods. The amine S-methyldithiocarbazate and its Schiff bases with ketones were synthesised by the reported methods^{2,5}.

Preparation of the complexes: The complexes were prepared by the direct interaction of Lewis acids with an excess of the ligand in dichloromethane under anhydrous conditions. In a representative experiment, a solution of antimony(III) chloride (1.14 g; 5 mmole) in dichloromethane (20 ml) was added dropwise under stirring to a solution of the Schiff base (HL-3) (2.24 g; 10 mmole) in the same solvent (5 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 2 hr after which the excess solvent was distilled off. Diethyl ether (15 ml) was added to the concentrate and the resulting solution kept overnight in a freezer. An intense orange coloured crystalline product separated. It was washed several times with diethyl ether and dried in vacuum.

Analyses and physical measurements: The complexes were analysed for antimony and halogen contents by reported methods^{6,7}. The conductance measurements of 10⁻³M solution of the complexes in freshly distilled dry nitrobenzene were made at 25° using a Philips PR 9500 conductivity bridge. Molecular weight of the complexes soluble in nitrobenzene were determined cryoscopically. The IR spectra of all the ligands and their complexes were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 521 spectrophotometer in the 4000-400 cm⁻¹ region. Complexes SbX₃.L-1 and SbCl₄.L-1 were also screened upto 200 cm⁻¹ in CsI phase on a Perkin Elmer 577 spectrophotometer.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA FOR Sb(III) AND Sb(V) COMPLEXES WITH SCHIFF BASES

Compound	m.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		IR absorption frequencies (cm ⁻¹)	
		Sb	Halogen	ν _{as} (CSS)	ν(C=N)
SbCl ₃ .L-1	156	34.79 (34.40)	19.87 (20.03)	1020 vs (1000 s)* 950 vs	1608 vs (1630 s)
SbBr ₃ .L-1	177	27.75 (27.49)	36.23 (36.09)	1005 s 945 vs	1590 vs
SbCl ₄ .L-1	124	28.78 (28.66)	32.37 (32.38)	1025 s 962 s	1625 s
SbCl ₃ .L-2	161	33.22 (33.09)	19.05 (19.27)	1020 s (1030 s) 980 vs	1590 vs (1630 s)
SbBr ₃ .L-2	186	27.01 (26.65)	34.68 (34.98)	1020 s 995 s	1595 vs
SbCl ₄ .L-2	132	27.73 (27.74)	32.48 (32.31)	1040 s 970 s	1630 br
SbCl ₃ .L-3	97	29.86 (29.27)	16.92 (17.04)	1085 s (1060 s) 1040 vs	1585 vs (1615 m)
SbBr ₃ .L-3	168	23.86 (24.11)	31.47 (31.65)	1085 vs 1040 vs	1585 vs
SbCl ₄ .L-3	129	25.16 (25.00)	28.86 (29.13)	1020 vs 1005 vs	1597 vs
SbCl ₃ .L-4	108	25.62 (25.47)	14.65 (14.83)	1070 vs (1000 vs) 1040 vs	1565 vs (1605 m)
SbBr ₃ .L-4	115	21.42 (21.47)	28.05 (28.19)	1085 vs 1020 vs	1580 vs
SbCl ₄ .L-4	138	21.82 (22.18)	26.00 (25.83)	1070 vs 1020 vs	1570 s

* Ligand absorptions in parantheses.

The analytical data and relevant ir absorptions along with their assignments are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are yellow to red in colour, insensitive to atmospheric air and do not decompose when heated to their melting point. The analytical data show that stoichiometries correspond to the formula $SbX_2 \cdot L$ ($X=Cl$ or Br) or $SbCl_4 \cdot L$ indicating the presence of the ligands in their deprotonated form. The molar conductance ($3.1-8.3 \text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$) of $10^{-3}M$ solutions of the complexes in nitrobenzene indicate the absence of ionic species and from the cryoscopic data for the complexes sufficiently soluble in nitrobenzene, it is concluded that they are monomeric and non-electrolytic, atleast, in solution.

The donor sites of the ligands have been identified on the basis of ir spectral data. The absence of characteristic absorptions attributable to the $\nu(NH)$ or $\nu(SH)$ in the spectra of the complexes indicates the deprotonation of the SH form of the bases (Ib) in presence of a Lewis acid. The deprotonation is enhanced due to the stabilization of the anion by conjugation with the >C=N-N=C< group⁸. Bonding through only one of the S atoms of the CSS group is inferred from the splitting of the strong $\nu_{as}(CSS)$ band^{9,10}. A band of medium to weak intensity appearing at $370 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of all the complexes of HL-1 (recorded upto 200 cm^{-1}) and being absent in the spectrum of the free Schiff base is tentatively assigned to the Sb-S stretching mode of vibration. The coordination through the N atom is indicated by the negative shift of $\nu(C=N)$ absorption frequency. The lowering is small, even negligible in a few cases, suggesting how little this mode of vibration is affected upon coordination¹¹. Bonding through both the N atoms is sterically not feasible and the involvement of the β -nitrogen in coordination is more likely as it gives rise to a five membered chelate ring with minimum strain.

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Preparation and Characterisation of Pyridine and 3-Picoline Adducts of Co(II) and Fe(II) Complexes

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IN continuation of our studies on metal complexes of different derivatives of 2-pyrazolin-5-ones^{1,2}, we report here the preparation and characterization of pyridine and 3-picoline adducts of Co(II) and Fe(II) complexes of 4-oximino-1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (OMPP), 4-oximino-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (OMP), 4-oximino-3-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (OPP) and 4-oximino-1,3-diphenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (ODPP).

Experimental

The chelating agents were prepared as described earlier². The hot ethanolic ligand solution containing 5 ml pyridine/3-picoline in slight excess over 1 : 2 metal : ligand ratio was added dropwise to the metal salt [$Co(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ or $FeSO_4 \cdot (NH_4)_2SO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$] solution in hot distilled water with constant stirring. The product was filtered, washed with cold water followed by ethanol and dried in air.

Metal content was estimated by titrating against standard EDTA solution after decomposing the complex. The thermograms of the compounds were recorded on 'Du Pont-950' thermogravimetric analyser. Other physico-chemical measurements were made as described earlier².

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) suggest 1 : 2 : 2 metal : ligand : base ratio in the complexes. The TGA studies gave the weight-loss (Table 1) of the compound and elimination temperature of the base and decomposition temperature of the compounds (Table 1).

The carbonyloximes are usually characterised by absorption due to C=O, C=N (oxime), N-O, O-H and C=N (cyclic) bonds. All ligands show strong and sharp band in the $1660-1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region